

Challenges in teaching speaking to young language learners

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ANNOTATION: This research explores the challenges and strategies associated with teaching English speaking skills to young learners in countries which English is not native, focusing on students learning English as a second or foreign language. The proficiency of speaking becomes one of the five skills

that should be acquired by every child in this 21st century era. Communicating and collaborating and language boundaries become a necessity in diverse and multinational communities. This research is aimed to investigate the teacher's strategies, problems and solutions for teaching speaking to young learners. This research has found several strategies promoted by the lecturer when teaching speaking to young learners. The teachers might face several barriers in the classroom such as reluctant students, missing pronunciation and lack of vocabularies. But he can overcome those barriers by using various techniques of teaching speaking to young learners, such as implementing media and designing the lesson using topical-based syllabus.

Key words: *Teaching strategies, Teaching Speaking, method, Speaking skill, technology, challenges, strategies, young learner, role-play activity.*

ANNOTATSIYA: Ushbu tadqiqot ingliz tili ona tili bo'lmagan mamlakatlardagi yosh o'quvchilarga ingliz tilini ikkinchi yoki xorijiy til sifatida o'rganishga qaratilgan holda ingliz tilini o'rganish bilan bog'liq

muammolar va strategiyalarni o'rganadi. Nutq mahorati XXI asrda har bir bola egallashi kerak bo'lgan beshta ko'nikmadan biriga aylanadi. Muloqot va hamkorlik va til chegaralari turli va ko'p millatli jamoalarda zaruratga aylanadi. Ushbu tadqiqot o'qituvchining yosh o'quvchilarga nutq so'zlashga o'rgatish strategiyalari, muammolari va echimlarini o'rganishga qaratilgan. Ushbu tadqiqot yosh o'quvchilarga nutq o'rgatishda o'qituvchi tomonidan ilgari surilgan bir qancha strategiyalarni topdi. O'qituvchilar sinfda istaksiz o'quvchilar, talaffuz va so'z boyligi etishmasligi kabi bir qator to'siqlarga duch kelishi mumkin. Ammo u bu to'siqlarni yosh o'quvchilarga nutq so'zlashga o'rgatishning turli usullaridan, masalan, ommaviy axborot vositalaridan foydalanish va mavzuga asoslangan o'quv dasturidan foydalangan holda darsni loyihalash orqali engib o'tishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: *O'qitish strategiyalari, Nutqni o'rgatish, usul, Nutq mahorati, texnologiya, qiyinchiliklar, strategiyalar, yosh o'quvchi, rolli o'yin faoliyati.*

АННОТАЦИЯ: В этом исследовании изучаются проблемы и стратегии, связанные с обучением навыкам разговорной речи на английском языке для молодых учащихся в странах, где английский язык не является родным, с упором на студентов, изучающих английский как второй или иностранный язык. Владение разговорной речью становится одним из пяти навыков, которые должен приобрести каждый ребенок в эпоху 21 века. Общение и сотрудничество, а также языковые границы становятся необходимостью в разнообразных и многонациональных сообществах. Целью данного исследования является изучение стратегий, проблем и решений учителя в обучении разговорной речи с юными учениками. Это исследование выявило несколько стратегий, продвигаемых лектором при обучении разговорной речи с юными учениками. Учителя могут столкнуться с несколькими препятствиями в классе, такими как неохотные ученики, отсутствие произношения и нехватка словарного запаса. Но он может преодолеть эти барьеры, используя различные методы обучения разговорной речи с

юными учениками, такие как использование средств массовой информации и разработка урока с использованием тематической программы.

Ключевые слова: Стратегии преподавания, Обучение говорению, метод, Навыки разговорной речи, технологии, задачи, стратегии, юный ученик, ролевая игра.⁴

The ability to effectively communicate in English is increasingly recognized as a critical skill in the globalized world. This has led to a significant emphasis on speaking abilities within the educational field, especially for young learners. However, teaching English speaking skills presents a unique set of challenges, particularly in ESL (English as a Second Language) and EFL (English as a Foreign Language) contexts. The mastery of speaking skills in English is a necessary for many second language and foreign language students. Therefore, learners often appraise their language learning on how much they think they have developed their skill in spoken language skill. Besides, the proficiency of speaking

becomes one of the five skills that should be acquired by every child in this 21-century era which is called as a communication skill. Further, communicating and collaborating and language boundaries become a necessity in diverse and multinational communities. Mutually beneficial relationships are a central undercurrent to accomplishment in Business. In preparing every child to have a good communication skill, teaching speaking is a primary requirement to be taught not only for adult learners but also for young learners.

As stated by Slattery and Willis (2001), cited in Hakim (2011), English is being provided into initial classroom, such as Kindergarten and Elementary school, so that the teachers are needed to teach it into young learners. Further, to make the children to be able to speak English in communication, teachers need to guide the students to acquire the vocabulary and structures.

In line with (Richard, 2008), Harmer (2007a, p. 123) proposes three major reasons for getting students to speak and to acquire new vocabulary in the classroom:

- 1). Speaking activities provide rehearsal opportunities
- 2). Speaking tasks in which students try to use any or all of the languages they know provide feedback for both teachers and students.
- 3). the more students have opportunities to activate the various language elements they have stored in their brains, the more automatic their use of these elements to become.

Meanwhile, teaching speaking to young learners may give some difficulties to the teacher especially in Indonesia, since the young learners also consider speaking as a great challenge since it requires them to speak and think at the same time. Besides, young learners are not necessarily competent communicators even in their mother tongue, and it reveals an idea that teaching speaking in Indonesia must be developed in EFL context. Speaking is a complex cognitive process and an active use of language to express meaning. It requires the language users to speak fluently, to be able to pronounce phonemes correctly, to use appropriate stress and intonation patterns, and to speak in connected speech. In line with Harmer (2007), Chaney (cited in Kayi, 2006) defines speaking as a

process of building and sharing meaning and information through the use of verbal and non-verbal symbols in variety context.

In EFL context, the language users are also urged to speak in different genres and situation, and they will have to be able to use a range of conversational and conversational repair strategies.

The goal of teaching speaking is communicative efficiency. Learners should be able to make themselves understood, using their current proficiency to the fullest. They should try to avoid confusion in the message due to faulty pronunciation, grammar, or vocabulary, and to observe the social and cultural rules that apply in each communication situation. To this relation, it is worth voting to what Nunan (2003) believes, which particularly dealing with teaching speaking. In his perception, to teach speaking can be defined as to teach the students to:

- Produce the English speech sound and sound patterns
- Use words and sentences stress, intonation patterns, and the rhythm of the second language

- Select the appropriate words and sentences according to the proper social setting, audience, situation and subject matter
- Organize their thoughts in a meaningful and logical sequence
- Use language as a mean of expressing values and judgments
- Use the language quickly and confidently with few unnatural pauses, which is called as fluency.

To help the students in developing communicative efficiency in speaking, teachers can use a balanced activities approach which combines language input, structured output, and communicative output.

Firstly, Language input comes in the form of teacher talk, listening activities, reading passages, and the language in which the students hear and read outside the class. It gives learners the material they need to begin producing language themselves. Language input may be *content oriented* or *form oriented*.

Secondly, structured output focuses on correct form. In structured output, students may have options for responses, but all of the options require them to use

the specific form or structure that the teacher has just introduced. *Structured output* is designed to make learners comfortable producing specific language items recently introduced, sometimes in combination with previously learned items. Instructors often use structured output exercises as a transition between the presentation stage and the practice stage of a lesson plan. Textbook exercises also often make good structured output practice activities.

Thirdly, communicative output, the learners' main purpose is to complete a task, such as obtaining information, developing a travel plan, or creating a video. To complete the task, they may use the language that the instructor has just presented, but they also may draw on any other vocabulary, grammar, and communication strategies that they know. In communicative output activities, the criterion of success is whether the learner gets the message across. Accuracy is not a consideration unless the lack of it interferes with the message. Paul (2003, p. 77) lists several principles that teachers need

to consider in preparing students to communicate in English:

1. Introducing and practicing patterns in ways that feel meaningful to the children, such as in games, in situation where the children genuinely want to express themselves, and through personalization.
2. Practicing new patterns in combination with the other patterns the children have learned, so the children can internalize them more easily.
3. Giving the children many opportunities to guess how to use the patterns flexibly in novel situation.
4. Giving the children confidence to speak out in front of others by talking independently with other children and the whole class.
5. Building the children's inner strength to deal with confusing and novel situations, by presenting them with puzzles to overcome and solve, and making sure, they are finally successful.

Focusing on the question forms of new patterns, so the children can ask about things they do not know. They can learn *Who is it?* before or at the same time as

learning, *it's a cat*, and, *what's she doing?* before or at the same time as learning *She's sleeping*. In line with Paul (2003), Harmer (2007b) and Terry (2008) classify roles of teacher in teaching speaking, as follows:

1. Prompter: The teachers provide the students with discrete suggestions, leave them to struggle by themselves, and give them chunks not words, without disrupting the discussion.

2. Participant: The teachers participate in the discussion by introducing new information and by ensuring the continuation of students' engagement. The main point is the teacher should not monopolize the conversation.

3. Feedback provider: The teachers can give some feedbacks by giving helpful and gentle correction and by telling the students about their performance. Besides that, they should avoid over-correction, since it might lead to students' reluctance to continue the dialogue.

4. Assessor: The teachers can write down some written samples of languages produced by students, or memorize some of it, then tell it to their students.

Young learner is categorized as students from ages three to eight years old (Wilson, 2003; Alianello, 2004). Pinter (2006) limits the age groups of young learners from five to fourteen years old. However, she offers an idea that age of categorization is not a big deal in teaching language to young learners. The main issue in teaching language to young learners should begin with the consideration that every child is unique and they have substantial differences within, such as the culture differences (Pinter, 2006). Moreover, Paul (2000) adds that all children deserve the chance to achieve their potential both as learners and as whole people, and become broad-minded members of a truly international society.

Brain Storming

On a given topic, students can produce ideas in a limited time. Depending on the context, either individual or group brainstorming is effective and learners generate ideas quickly and freely. The good characteristic of brainstorming is that the students are not criticized for their ideas so students will be open to sharing new ideas.

Storytelling

Students can briefly summarize a tale or story they heard from somebody beforehand, or they may create their own stories to tell their classmates. Story telling fosters creative thinking. It also helps students express ideas in the format of beginning, development, and ending, including the characters and setting a story has to have.

Information Gap

In this activity, students are supposed to be working in pairs. One student will have the information that other partner does not have and the partners will share their information. Information gap activities serve many purposes such as solving a problem or collecting information. Also, each partner plays an important role because the task cannot be completed if the partners do not provide the information the others need.

Story Completion

For this activity, a teacher starts to tell a story, but after a few sentences he or she stops narrating. Then, each student starts to narrate from the point where the previous one stopped. Each student is supposed to add

from four to ten sentences. Students can add new characters, events, descriptions and so on.

Picture Describing

For this activity students can form groups and each group is given a different picture. Students discuss the picture with their groups, and then a spokesperson for each group describes the picture to the whole class. This activity fosters the creativity and imagination of the learners as well as their public speaking skills.

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